

Research

Sloshing Assessment and Development of Small Scale LNG Carrier Containment System

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Abstract: This study explores the sloshing phenomena that occur when transporting Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) in membrane tank LNG carriers. The sloshing phenomenon becomes more important as the volume of the tank increases. The study presents an evaluation of a membrane-type LNG containment system with a capacity of 19,000 cubic meters, using the program ANSYS Fluent to construct the mesh and simulate the LNG sloshing motion. The impact pressure, which affects the tank wall strength and the vessel's stability, is investigated, and the study finds that liquid depth affects the higher impact pressure for circular motion in contrast to horizontal motion. The study also reveals that using a blanket over the liquid's surface can significantly reduce the higher impact pressure. These findings provide insights into how to successfully lower the impact pressure to ensure the structural integrity of the bulkheads in real-world scenarios.

Keywords: *Transportation of Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG), LNG cargo sloshing, Anti-Sloshing blanket, Insulation system strength*

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1. Introduction

Green energy is gaining popularity throughout the world as concern for the environment becomes more mainstream. In the transition away from the current energy infrastructure, natural gas is a key component. Shipping Liquefied Natural Gas is the cheapest means of transport when compared to other options like pipelines and trains. Cases of incomplete fulfillment are inevitable now that the spot market exists. When the tank is empty, liquid will spill out [1]. When the LNG tank is moving at a frequency equivalent to or near the natural frequency of the interaction between the LNG and the tank structure, the sloshing motion will be strong even if the tank is only partly full [2]. Therefore, it is essential that the LNG carrier can be run without risk at any level of liquid cargo.

For a long time, researchers have been trying to figure out how to prevent liquid sloshing in an LNG tank, as this is a serious problem in the maritime business. When a ship's tank sloshes about, it may generate powerful impact forces that cause the vessel to become unstable or even capsize. A ship's structure can be damaged, for example by the rupture of internal pipelines, if the LNG tank is subjected to a strong sloshing motion. The sloshing also increase the

boil of gas rate daily and it cause efficiency of insulation system [3]. The gas will leak or the ship will explode because of the weakened hull. It's possible that human lives would be lost and the environment would be harmed as a result of these mishaps. This means that it is crucial to the design of an LNG tank to be able to accurately forecast the sloshing phenomena of the liquid inside. This study provides a brief synopsis of current studies on the use of the blanket to control liquid sloshing and reviews the methods used to investigate the sloshing phenomena.

In relation to the sloshing loads in LNG tanks, multiple ship structural issues have been identified [4]. Since the active advances of LNG vessels and FPSO in the oil and energy business in these years, the sloshing phenomena in ship containers have been drawing numerous study interests. Hydrodynamic pressure distribution, forces, moments, and natural frequencies of the surface layer are the core concerns of hydraulic sloshing [5].

The shipbuilding industry is becoming more invested in the research and development of robust and dependable anti-sloshing systems to address the sloshing problem and ensure the safe delivery of risky liquid bulks over maritime routes. In the case of a liquefied natural gas (LNG) plant, anti-sloshing equipment are especially useful when liquid levels are between full and half full. Resonance sloshing is inherent in a working LNG carrier because to the frequent variations in liquid level caused by LNG manufacturing and discharge [6]. Baffles are commonly used to minimize the movement and influence of sloshing liquids [7–10]. Researchers discovered that LNG sloshing in a half loaded membrane tank with a anti-sloshing blanket on the tank's above was much reduced. The sloshing in LNG tanks can be mitigated using the tried-and-true approach of set up a anti-sloshing blanket [9, 10] on the liquid container. This anti-sloshing device does have some drawbacks, however, including the fact that it can be broken by particularly violent liquid sloshing, that it degrades the insulation performance [11], and that it needs to be inspected frequently because of the long-term fatigue problem in cryogenic conditions [12].

2. Analyze Methods and Techniques

Because of its practical significance, research into fluid sloshing has a long history and continues to garner significant attention. The effects of sloshing are often studied using one of three methods: experimental [13,14], theoretical analytic [15,16], or computational [17,18].

In analyzing the sloshing effect load in an LNG tank, Abramson et al. [13] made a significant addition to the experimental technique. The experimental method allows for the incorporation of more complex physical phenomena linked to sloshing than the alternatives. These phenomena include the compress rate influence of the liquid during impact, air entrapment, the elastic influence of the ship wall, etc. The problems with the experimental method, however, can't be ignored. Even though the form of the prototype is straightforward, running a test takes a long time and a large number of impacts. In addition, the impact load is tricky to accurately scale from the prototype to full scale [13]. It is the classification organizations (ABS - American Bureau of Shipping) that are currently the most prominent users of the experimental method.

In most situations, the sloshing phenomenon is caused by turbulent fluid flow, which leads to a nonlinear issue. As there is no analytic solution to this highly nonlinear issue, computational approaches, such as computational fluid dynamics are used to corroborate experimental results [19]. Finite-difference technique is used by Faltinsen & Timokha [20] to model LNG tank sloshing. Finite-element analysis is another well-liked technique [17, 18, 21, 22]. By solving the Navier-Stokes equation numerically, the computational technique represents the mathematical method. Commercial CFD programs like Star-CCM and Fluent are mature and widely used at this point. The computing technique is straightforward to implement and precise enough to mimic sloshing in an LNG tank [23], as evidenced by the excellent accordance between the computational and experimental results.

Given the difficulties inherent in the current LNG shipping infrastructure along the sea route, a novel approach is needed to guarantee safer LNG transport by mitigating the risk of dangerous sloshing during transit. Previous studies [24, 25] developed an anti-sloshing floater to control the liquid surface elevation, therefore lowering the contact stress

along the longitudinal bulkhead. Both experimental and numerical approaches were employed to examine the floater, and the results supported the researchers' conclusion that it effectively mitigates liquid peaks. In addition, a floater-type blanket anti-sloshing device was proposed [26], and its impacts on sloshing motion were studied through a series of prototype tank tests. It has been claimed that sloshing may be effectively muted by using floaters [24, 25] and a foam blanket [26] made from melamine resin. The results demonstrated that at low filling condition, the overall reduction of sloshing pressure is more noticeable.

This research examines the efficacy of a blanket system with a spherical form in decreasing liquid sloshing. These approaches have been tested experimentally to see effective at preventing the liquid in the prototype tank from sloshing around in response to the random, stimulated, one-directional motion. The height of the liquid in relation to the tank's walls is used to calculate the sloshing impact.

3. Experimental Discussion

The sloshing phenomena in a two-dimensional LNG tank is modeled and simulated using the commercial Computational Fluid Dynamic program Fluent v13.0. The ANSYS FLUENT 13.0 User's Guide [27] provides more information on the numerical approaches.

The hit pressure during the simulation is recorded by pressure sensors, which are shown and located in the schematic diagram of a two-dimensional membrane tank with a single layer floater type anti-sloshing blanket covering up the liquid surface in Figure 1. Additionally, the dispersed 14 spheres with $\varnothing 10\text{cm}$ are transformed into an anti-sloshing blanket by being tied together in a structure using polyarylate fiber threads. Collective impacts in anti-sloshing can be contributed by the blanket because the movement of a single floater inside a blanket is associated with and constrained by its neighbors. The membrane tank has a length (L) of 2.0 meters and a height (H) of 1.5 meters (H). Both the bottom and top chamfers on this membrane tank are 45 degrees in angle, and their respective dimensions are 20cm by 20cm meters and 40cm by 40cm. In the absence of an anti-sloshing blanket, the liquid filling level (h) is assumed to be at 30%, 55%, and 70% of the container's height, corresponding to the positions of pressure sensors 3, 4, and 5, respectively. Pressure sensors 2 and 6 are centered on the lower and upper chamfer, while sensors 1 and 7 are positioned in the center of the tank's base and apex. Liquid filling level is calculated as 30% of the container height in situations with anti-sloshing blanket.

Figure.1 The diagram depicts the layout of a 2D membrane tank equipped with an anti-sloshing blanket and pressure sensors.

Without anti-sloshing blanket situations, the sloshing movement of liquid in a membrane tank is first simulated. Any kind of movement, be it horizontal or rotary, is taken into account. The excitation frequency of the membrane tank

is tuned to be the same as the natural frequency of the tank itself. There are three predetermined liquid fill levels of 30%, 50%, and 75% of the tank's total depth. Pressure sensors mounted to the inside of the tank measure the force exerted by the liquid as it strikes the surface. Impact pressure registered by sensors 3 for 30% liquid filling level, 4 for 55% liquid filling level, and 5 for 70% liquid filling depth level, which may illustrate a better fluctuation of the impact pressure during the sloshing action are shown.

Table 1 summarizes our simulated case studies for this investigation. The first nine cases do not have designed the anti-sloshing blanket . The anti-sloshing blanket is installed in cases 10-13.

Tabel.1 The summary results of cases which simulated.

Case No	Fill Depth h (m)	Motion Amplitude Pitching (m), Rolling (deg.)	Excited Frequency
1	0.30	0.1	2.963 rad/s
2	0.30	0.2	3.612 rad/s
3	0.55	0.2	3.905 rad/s
4	0.70	0.2	4.345 rad/s
5	0.30	7 deg.	3.612 rad/s
6	0.30	14 deg.	3.612 rad/s
7	0.55	7 deg.	3.905 rad/s
8	0.55	14 deg.	3.905 rad/s
9	0.70	7 deg.	4.345 rad/s
10	0.30	0.1	5.132 rad/s
11	0.30	0.2	5.132 rad/s
12	0.30	7 deg.	5.132 rad/s
13	0.30	14 deg.	5.132 rad/s

4. Without the anti-sloshing blanket cases

Before the anti-sloshing cases are introduced, the sloshing movement of the liquid in the membrane container is simulated. Movements in the vertical and rotary axes are taken into account. It is common practice to use the membrane tank's natural frequency as the excitation frequency for a periodic sinusoidal wave that is used to excite the tank. There are three predetermined liquid fill levels of 30%, 55%, and 70% of the tank's total depth. The pressure sensors mounted to the tank's inside wall measure the force exerted by the liquid when it strikes the surface. The impact pressure collected by the sensors that show a better fluctuation of the impact pressure during the sloshing movement is provided; these sensors are numbered 3, 4, and 5, respectively, for 30%, 55%, and 70% of the container's volume being filled with liquid.

Figure.2 Three liquid filling levels (30%, 55%, and 70% of tank depth), 0.02 motion amplitude pitching motion.

Figure.3 Three liquid filling levels (30%, 55%, and 70% of tank depth), rolling motion with 8° motion amplitude.

Different liquid filling depths for pitching and rolling motions are depicted in Figures 5 and 6, respectively, to show the impact pressure experienced during the liquid sloshing action. Looking at the two numbers side by side, we can see that the influence of liquid depth on the maximum impact pressure for circular motion is more nuanced than it is for horizontal movement. Figure 5 illustrates that when the excitation frequency is adjusted to the natural frequency and the motion amplitude is held constant, the impact pressure during sloshing movement is little affected by the depth of the liquid. On the other hand, as shown in Figure 6, a higher impact pressure is generated by a lower liquid filling level when the object is in a rotational movement.

Changes in the liquid phase due to the sloshing movement are seen in Figure 7. Cases 1, 4, and 5 show the distortion of the liquid phase during horizontal movement without the anti-sloshing blanket. The figures clearly show that the non-linearity of the liquid motion increases with depth. Liquid splashing and wave breaking are phenomena that are seen at greater depths.

Figure.4 The motion conditions for the liquid sloshing in the membrane tank are listed in Table.1 for both the anti-sloshing blanket and without anti-sloshing blanket situations.

4.1 Sloshing control using anti-sloshing blanket

In the absence of an anti-sloshing blanket, the impact pressure is greater for smaller volumes of liquid. When the tank is only partially full of liquid, the maximum impact pressure on the tank wall can be managed by installing an anti-sloshing blanket on the liquid surface all over the tank. Figure 8 shows a comparison of the impact pressure for a rolling motion with a 14deg. movement amplitude, and it can be observed that the impact pressure is greatly reduced for cases with an anti-sloshing blanket, as compared to the non anti-sloshing blanket condition. Figure 9 depicts the drop in pressure due to impact in different scenarios. Results show that the maximum impact pressure is drop by approximately half when tanks with anti-sloshing blanket compared to those with no such blanket on the surface of the liquid.

The membrane tank's natural frequency may be changed by installing an anti-sloshing blanket on the surface of the liquid. If we compare the new natural frequency to the old one, we find that its value has roughly doubled. Because of this, we are able to prevent the resonance phenomena that happened at the first stimulated frequency.

Figure.5 Comparisons between with and without anti-sloshing blanket show 30% liquid filling level and 14deg. motion amplitude.

Figure.6 The maximum impact pressure for cases with and without baffle is 30% of tank depth, and motion direction and amplitude are specified below each bar.

5. Analysis of the Insulation's Strength

The Mark III containment system plane stress prototype was finished following ABS guidelines [28]. The orthotropical characteristic of plywood sheets and other temperature-dependent component features of reinforced polyurethane foam (R-PUF) were considered. All 47,800 of the model's rectangles were subjected to the same stress distribution (See Fig. 7). Similar to the design sloshing load set in Chapter 4, this pressure number was also spot on.

Figure.7 Membrane tanker wall insulation FE prototype in two dimensions.

There were two FE algorithms used for the static FE Simulation prototype. There were two sets of requirements that needed to be satisfied: the efficiency standard and the serviceability limit standard. The former indicates that the computed stress components from the FEM were compared to the permitted values for the respective materials. This second scenario implies that the displacement fields were gathered to ensure that allowable deformations would be maintained. Both the horizontal (as shown in Fig. 9) and vertical (as shown in Fig. Figure 8 shows the results of an examination into the tensile force and Von Mises-equivalent stress distributions.

Figure.8 Equal stress distribution across the membrane. The plywood layer had the highest average (4.49 MPa).

Figure.9 Distribution of horizontal compression and tension stresses in the membrane wall.

Upon further analysis, it was determined that the estimated values of the aforementioned stress components did not surpass the permissible levels for any of the layers. These findings led to the conclusion that the insulating system's static strength was adequate. It looked at the possibility of transitory impacts in the insulation system brought on by the dynamically varying load. This was accomplished using a time-dependent load scenario used in a transient FE simulation. The pressure applied to the upper surface was a triangular impulse superimposed over a step function.

Figure.10 depicts the system's reaction. After conducting a thorough dynamic analysis, the team determined that the system's intrinsic time period is around 50 percent that of a normal sloshing pressure impact. To put it another way, the practical implication is that the static simulation revealed enough data on the insulating materials' strength.

Figure.10 Von Mises-equivalent plywood stress for step function and triangle impulse.

6. Analysis of the Hull's Strength

FEM was used to measure the stability of the steel framework that holds up the membrane layers. For the numerical study, we focused on a single plate area since the barrier is essentially a network of steel shells braced by extremely rigid longitudinal and transverse frames. Local longitudinal reinforcements add even more strength to this plate field. ABS criteria found in Refs. [29] and [30] were used to calculate the geometrical measurements, such as frame spacing and plate thickness. Two-dimensional quadratic shell elements were used in the finite element model. The 9% Nickel-alloyed steel used in the construction of this item was sourced from reference [31]. At -196 degrees Celsius, the impact energy of this material is 27Joul , and its yield strength is 515 MPa. With a uniform pressure load applied to the plating, static FE simulations were run to determine the displacement fields and stress distributions.

Figure.11 Intentional sloshing load causes deformation of the reinforced steel frame.

For a 2.4 m × 3 m plate surface, the maximum allowable deformation was 8 mm. In Fig. 11, we see the steel framework deforming on a larger-than-life size. Analytical calculations were used to assess the effectiveness of the numerical technique, as described in [32]. Less than half of the yield strength, 236 MPa, was calculated as the Von Mises-equivalent stress. Extreme shear stress in the plating was 181 MPa, which is much less than the 299 MPa shear strength. Based on these numbers, it was determined that the steel framework's strength was enough.

7. Conclusions

From this study, there are following conclusions have been drawn:

- ◆ This study details a series of experiments designed to determine whether or not anti-sloshing blankets are effective. We put the model through its paces by simulating two different scenarios: (1) free surface alone, and (2) with an anti-sloshing blanket with three different filling levels of 30%, 55% and 70%, respectively.

1) Maximum impact pressure is more affected by liquid depth for rotating motion than by horizontal motion. An increased impact force is produced by a rotary motion with a decreased liquid filling level.

2) The motion and impact pressure of liquid sloshing may be considerably reduced by setting up an anti-sloshing blanket above the LNG of the membrane tank. When comparing examples with and without an anti-sloshing blanket on the fluid surface of the tanker, the maximum impact pressure for the tank with an anti-sloshing blanket is lowered by about 50%.

◆ Static FE analysis can be used to study how sloshing affects the bulkheads' durability. The sloshing phenomenon is affected by the tank's filling level in the following ways:

1) Sloshing pressure amplitudes decrease as the volume increases.

2) Hydrodynamic pressure decreases as the fill level rises.

3) Simultaneously, the total of these two pressures, the maximal pressure value, stays relatively constant.

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